

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract:

This article describes the importance of intercultural communication competence in foreign language learning. Here we can also consider the extent to which intercultural communication has been studied or the history of the field. So, our research will focus on these areas with the purpose of finding out the useful sides of intercultural communication competence in foreign language learning.

Key words: culture, grammar, target language, ethnicity, intercultural competence

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Recent studies that have researched reasons why learning culture is thought to be an important part of the foreign language learning experience have proved that it is a relevant issue in the linguistics field and consequently that intercultural communicative competence must be taught simultaneously. These studies have also pointed the importance of the sociocultural context when learning a foreign language, and consequently the interactions needed to develop intercultural communicative competence in foreign language learners. Theoretical research into foreign language learning often uses terms such as ‘cultural competence’, ‘the intercultural dimension’, ‘intercultural communicative competence’ and there are continuous references to the importance of understanding cultures and learning about cultural communication in the foreign language learning process.

The importance of intercultural communication competence is emphasized within the domain of foreign languages because language is considered a tool of informing and transferring thoughts, knowledge, ideas, emotions, events.

According to Schmidt there is a two-way relationship between language and culture. The use of language correlates with culture which dominate foreign cultures; therefore, apart from being acquainted with the basic principles of grammar and the lexicon, it is necessary to be acquainted with the extra-linguistic factors of a specific speech and cultural community. It is known that language and culture complement each other; it is essential to study them equally because one needs to be acquainted with language as a system for the purpose of intercultural communication, as well as with cultural patterns which are characteristic of the target language and culture.

The definition of intercultural competence given by well-known scientist emphasized the ability of individuals to relate and communicate effectively with

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others who do not share the same culture, ethnicity, language or other important difference. Intercultural competence - a part of the foreign language learner's broad competence of speaking another language - identifies the ability of a person to act appropriately and flexibly when confronted with actions, attitudes and expectations of people from other cultures. The ability for language learners to stabilize their own identity in the process of mediation between cultures and help others to stabilize theirs. One of the reasons, intercultural competence is so important to language learners is because much of people's culturally motivated behavior occurs at a subconscious level; learners need to be aware of this is because it will help them better understand the messages members of those cultures are sending which are not verbalized or obvious and the many meanings that may be hidden from them.

One of the most important changes in language learning and teaching over the past decades has been the recognition of the cultural dimension as a key component. This change has transformed the nature of the experience of teaching and learning languages to a great extent. The objective of language learning is no longer defined in terms of the acquisition of communicative competence in a foreign language, which refers to a person's ability to act in a foreign language in linguistically, socio-linguistically and pragmatically appropriate ways.

Culture in Second and Foreign learning it's observed that language is employed in a cultural phenomenon to exchange minds and opinions or share experience. It is such a lot interrelated that without understanding properly the cultural setting and social behavior of a language use, it results in misinterpretation and breakdown within the language communication, or it is going to result into errors and misunderstanding because language is not simply sending or receiving information but it functions as a social behavior in certain cultural context. There are difficulties which are very complex to know for foreign or second language learners consistent with required context to interpret and communicate.

Research on the field of English teaching shows problems faced by the learners in communicating language in context. Variety of language instructed programs specialize in the event of skills, listening, speaking, reading, and writing but the teaching cultural has not been introduced in any of the learning programs.

However, the understanding culture not only develops competence in communication but also raises awareness regarding the utilization of language in intercultural communication. Competence in intercultural communication is that the ability of an individual's understanding of key issues involved within the communication of language in culturally different contexts. Cultural differences convey dissimilar meanings and values attached to a social organization demanding an excellent deal of understanding on the part of speakers participating in intercultural communication. It even requires higher level of communication skills to form sense of the meaning communicated in culturally diverse contexts. Furthermore, the studies on intercultural communication not only determine the role of competence but also advise the understanding of cultural awareness for meaningful communication.

There are different of intercultural communicative situations during which participants are hoped to behave appropriately as per the cultural context of communication. This behavioral aspect of interaction greatly involves an individual's capacity of adjusting to new cultures. An individual's capacity of

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adapting to new conventions reflect how suitable actions are added to avoid ambiguity in intercultural communication. The goal of teaching becomes the ability to communicate in a foreign language. The content of teaching a foreign language is focused on the formation and development of all components of communicative competence: speaking skills and abilities, which are created on the basis of language, linguo-cultural knowledge and country studies.

The topic of intercultural competence became more and more important during the past years: globalization and worldwide contacts between companies, organizations and individuals need the ability to communicate in a successful way. Core needs are sensitivity and self-consciousness: the understanding of other behaviors and ways of thinking as well as the ability to express one's own point of view in a transparent way with the aim to be understood and respected by staying flexible where this is possible, and clear and transparent where this is necessary.

As some points out, teachers of languages often agree that target languages should be taught alongside their cultures. If the foreigner would like to become familiar with a new culture, often the culture of the foreign language they are studying, they must go through a learning process, which is usually long and arduous, as, although exactly the same categories exist in their culture, the content and interpretation of these categories and thus reactions and behaviors towards them is completely different; for a member of another group to understand the same concept in a different way or to view them from a different perspective is not easy, which is why the learner should be taught the different possible ways of interpreting them or at least be made aware of them and that there are many ways of reacting to them.

The system of foreign language teaching is being modeled. It provides the development of intellectual aspects of the student's personality: in the process of comparing different conceptual systems, the worldview of a learner is enriched through intercultural reality and means of picture of world structuring. Culturally forming system of a foreign language education, modeled in the certain level of foreign language teaching, is based on the principles of time-tested national education system and the basic principles of the world's education systems and the functioning of the forecast model under changing socioeconomic conditions. The principle of communicative and intercultural interaction provides the development of students' ability to intercultural dialogue in other languages.

Culture used to be taught in language learning class as the literature, facts and geography of the target language, this was a simplification of culture, what he calls the fours; food, fairs, folklore and statistical facts. When anthropology began to study culture the idea that culture did not only exist as facts and information began to take root and began to be seen as something that is shared between members of a group and as more deeply rooted. It is not possible to teach learners how to internalize the culture of the language they are learning but they can understand the differences between cultures, by learning about the different cultural dimensions, which can eventually result in a deeper understanding of that culture when those learners then go on to experience and live in or interact with that culture.

References:

- [1]. Heacox D. (2002) *Differentiation Instruction in the Regular Classroom: How to Reach and Teach All Learners*, Minneapolis, MN: Free Spirit.
- [2]. Heacox, D. (2005). *Promoting Student Independence and Responsibility in Academically Diverse Classrooms*. 2005 ASCD Annual Conference. Orlando, FL.
- [3]. Nunley, K. E. (2006). *Differentiating the High School Classroom: Solution Strategies for 18 Common Obstacles*. Thousand Oaks: CA: Corwin.
- [4]. Tomlinson, C. A., & Allan, S. D. (2000). *Leadership for Differentiating Schools and Classrooms*.
- [5]. Wormeli, R. (2006). *Fair Isn't Always Equal: Assessing & Grading in the Differentiated Classroom*. Portland, ME: Stenhouse.